

Information Governance: the interest groups plans; what is IG?; and federation

Organised by UK TRE community and the DARE UK Information Governance interest group, March 26th 2025.

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The agenda:

The registration details for the event held are [here](#) ¹

This event continues a series of events organised by the UK TRE that focus on federation of TREs / SDEs and the impact that approach has on key aspects affecting this community. Prior ones have looked at

- Federation (Sept 2024)
- Public Involvement and Engagement (Dec 2024)
- Funding and Sustainability (Jan 2025)

This event was focussed on Information Governance (IG) within a federated world. It was co-organised with the DARE UK funded Information Governance interest group, led by Kate O'Sullivan at Sheffield with co-chairs at Edinburgh University, The Francis Crick Institute, the University of West England and a member of the public recruited through UseMyData.

An analysis of the registration data provided by the participants showed potential attendees were split 45% people self-classifying as "non IG" and 55% self-classifying "IG" people. Of the 79 registered 45 people (57%) attended the session.

The event had the following agenda

- 09:30 - 09:40 – Welcome and introductions
- 09:40 - 10:00 – **CMWG update** / announcements and Working Group updates
- 10:00 – 10:15 – **Icebreaker** – “What is Information Governance to you?”
- 10:15 – 10:40 – **The IG interest group**, and presenting the pre-reading material
- 10:40 – 10:50 – *Grab a tea / coffee / water... back at 10:50 if you can please*
- 10:50 – 11:50 – **Community discussion** on the presented views and vision for IG
- 11:50 - 12:00 – *Grab a tea / coffee / water... back before 12:00 please*
- 12:00 - 12:20 – **Federated Governance** – the Scottish experience and learnings so far.
Kathy Harrison: DataLoch
- 12:20 - 12:50 – **Discussion** on this and the vision
- 12:50 – 13:00 – Wrap up and Close

Materials available in addition to this event summary:

- The session slides presented and the Federated Governance presentation are [here](#) ²
- The pre-reading material circulated is available [here](#) ³:
- The YouTube recording is [here](#) ⁴:
- And the summary of the zoom chat is [here](#) ⁵:
- The HackMD notes of the meeting are [here](#) ⁶

¹ Registration page: <https://lu.ma/nm27fo56>

² Session slides: <https://zenodo.org/records/15195458> see introduction deck and see federated governance deck

³ Pre reading material: <https://zenodo.org/records/15083688>

⁴ Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TEU46GAPOjo>

⁵ Zoom chat summary:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1KAzwle66nngn1xgdyZCKL3tW0BKF3U2QTsrko7DTq5I/edit?tab=t.0>

⁶ HackMD meeting notes: <https://hackmd.io/WaBEcoWYTD6g0JmH9facGg?both>

UK TRE Working Group Summary:

This material is available [here](#) ⁷:

The Community Management Working Group (CMWG) led by the UK TRE co-chairs summarised their work, done behind the scenes, for the community:

- Presented to the UK Health Data Research Alliance Council meeting: 5th February: An overview of the UK TRE activities with a focus on financial sustainability
- Presented to the DARE UK Public Event on Communities: 24th February : An overview of UK TRE community, its composition and activities.
- Organising the annual Conference alongside other DARE UK supported community groups
 - SDC-Reboot interest group
 - Secure Data Access Professionals (SDAP) interest group
 - Information Governance interest group
 - SATRE interest group
- Preparing for the end of The Turing Institute's superb support for this community group that is happening at the end of April 2025. Documenting, reorganising, website changes.
- Issued the [Community Principles](#) ⁸:

The UK TRE Community has seven chartered working groups. Each of the groups then had the opportunity to summarise recent activity. The following is a top level view of those activities – the group looking at the cybersecurity risks for TREs was unable to attend:

[Funding & Sustainability](#) Jan 28th see [YouTube](#) here ⁹

[Citizen Agency](#): Event Dec 3rd 2024 see [YouTube](#) here ¹⁰

[SDE / TRE Definitions](#) Development work has finished with survey results analysed. Now transferring into other areas:

- **SATRE** – formalising the separation of the Data Zone from the Research Zone.
- **Information Governance** – extending control between Data Zones and federated Research Zones
- **Funding and Sustainability** – organising the funding of Data Zone and Research Zone operations.

[Extending Control](#) between Data and Research Zones. The time has not been right to issue the Request for Input. But now there is an advantage because of:

- The potential involvement of the new Information Governance interest group
- The possible Tech session planned for the UK TRE Community in June / July

[Glossary](#): Version 1 of Glossary complete! Publication imminent. Working on mechanism to capture new entries/modify current entries

[SATRE](#) Funded by DARE UK communities grant and TREvolution. Focus for 2025: SATRE v2

- Incorporating feedback from the community
- Extending SATRE to support federation
- Finding a sustainable Governance model for SATRE
- Looking at making SATRE into a formal accreditation

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/15195458> see working group updates deck

⁸ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Nqmkc2N-n0EgHODYk_KD_vy0ewZi2I3UclU0vQkFh-s/edit?usp=sharing

⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dz-ZqseE7aM>

¹⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DgBm6Ibqir0&t=99s>

“Please can you respond to the Zoom poll:

- *This is to collect names (poss emails) to reach out to, as part of the interest group’s activities. Don’t respond if you do not want to!”*

Pre-reading: 5 views of Information Governance

Prior to the event some pre-reading was shared with all those registered to attend. At the event the link to this material was also shared.

Yvonne Adebola, the public co-chair of the IG interest group, presented the five views, using the slides 28-32 in the Zenodo published deck [here](#)¹²:

The meeting then discussed points that arose from these, answering and engaging in a variety of questions, including: Are these views very different from those you understand? Was there anything surprising? What is stopping us having a consistent model of IG? What is not in IG’s scope?

See the YouTube recording [here](#), the HackMD discussion [here](#), and the zoom chat summary [here](#) that captures the discussion points. A summary is here:

- Participants raised concerns about the ongoing challenge of balancing **open data access** for researchers while ensuring **data privacy** and protecting sensitive information. Several attendees noted that current frameworks often rely on restrictive access models that can hinder research progress – but are important to consider especially with little case law on privacy and the desires of researchers to push new boundaries (e.g. AI)
- There was a consensus that **data access frameworks, risk appetites, IG understanding and contexts** vary significantly across institutions and sectors. This fragmentation makes it difficult to create a unified, interoperable system. Participants suggested that UKTRE should prioritise **promoting IG as an enabler/improver of research** and **harmonising data governance standards** to reduce administrative burdens for researchers – however an acknowledgement that this needs to be agile as IG is a constantly evolving field.
- 65% of attendees felt a harmonised model for IG in TREs (for sensitive data research) could be reached within a year.
- An enjoyable debate was had around where IG begins and ends – some TREs consider IG to cover all aspects of operations. There was an agreed analogy of IG being less of a direct balance and more of a jigsaw puzzle that concerns whether all pieces are in place (e.g. security, ethics, data protection, contracts, risk assessments, training etc) to create the full picture for research to take place safely and securely. IG should be satisfied all are in place, without being the expert on any.
- Some attendees highlighted the **complexity of governance structures**, particularly in large-scale collaborative projects. Questions are raised in each project about which entities would be responsible for enforcing data governance rules, monitoring compliance, and handling data misuse – therefore models of access are important.
- Participants pointed out that TREs can struggle to scale effectively. They often work well for pilot projects but face challenges when expanding to support national or international research collaborations. The discussion touched on the need for **federated models** that allow data to remain distributed while providing controlled access.
- Concerns were raised about the lack of **transparency** and **auditability** in AI model development and deployment within TREs. Attendees discussed how the **GRAIMATTER project** developed guidelines for responsible AI egress from TREs, suggesting that UKTRE could adopt similar frameworks to ensure models are properly governed and reproducible.

¹² <https://zenodo.org/records/15195458>

- Cross-border (outwith UK) research collaborations present additional challenges, especially in complying with **data protection regulations** like GDPR. Participants debated how UKTRE could support international research while ensuring legal and ethical compliance. Some suggested **data use agreements** with standardised templates can simplify the process.
- Attendees emphasized that even well-designed systems are ineffective without adequate researcher training and other training. It was suggested that UKTRE provide **programmes and workshops** to familiarise users with data governance requirements, secure data handling practices and common understandings of risk.
- The lack of clear **accountability frameworks** was another concern. Participants proposed developing mechanisms for independent audits, establishing clear lines of responsibility, and maintaining transparent reporting processes to build trust in the system.
- Finally, the conversation touched on the sustainability of TREs. Participants suggested that projects like UKTRE should consider how to ensure continued funding, operational resilience, and adaptability to future technological changes.

Federated Governance: Kathy Harrison - DataLoch (South-East Scotland Safe Haven):

Kathy Harrison (DataLoch (South-East Scotland Safe Haven)) gave a summary presentation of the work across the Scottish Safe Haven network to align the Information Governance to allow for federation in support of research projects. The Scottish Safe Havens offer significant strengths and have a long history of operation (see Figure 2) across most Health Boards in Scotland (Figure 3)

Figure 2: Data strengths in Scotland and the Scottish Safe Havens

NHS Research Scotland Regional Nodes Major Research Boards and Scottish Safe Havens

Figure 3: The five NHS Boards involved in the Safe havens across Scotland.

The approach was to adopt an “EQUIVALENCE” not a “STANDARDISATION” approach. The [SATRE framework](#)¹³ was used to evaluating each Safe Haven independently, and through comparison of the results, identify focus areas for discussion. By combining with a model for what federated governance was and was not, see Figure 4, a sense of mutual understanding of others’ approaches, policies and solutions resulted. This understanding lead to “equivalence” and towards mutual trust.

Federated Governance: Key features of the solution

What is it?	What is it not?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Project level data-sharing of de-identified data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> x Sharing of identifiable patient level data
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Federated governance: governance terms agreed centrally, but local domains have autonomy and resources to execute these standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> x Wholesale sharing of data
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Equivalence of standards: maintaining equivalent security and privacy protections, despite different processes and technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> x Proactive sharing of data (not sharing data in advance of project level extraction)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Delegated approvals: reviews and approvals undertaken within one Safe Haven accepted as delegated approval for all 4 regional Safe Havens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> x Data-sharing outside of Safe Haven TREs

Figure 4: What Federated Governance is and is not – for the harmonisation discussions across the Scottish Safe Havens.

Careful scoping was used:

In scope:

- Enabling academic research in the NHS
- Research to support service improvement
- Health board coverage: existing health boards who are part of Safe Haven data
- Ethical peer review and Caldicott approval

Out of scope:

- Data-sharing outwith project extracts
- Identifiable patient level data

¹³ <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/>

With any work, scope is key, and at present the Scottish Federated Governance programme consider the following out of scope for Phase 1:

- international projects,
- private or 3rd sector or Machine Learning (ML/AI) (this is planned for Phase 2 in 2026);
- or work with free text or image and omics data being part of a later phase.
- Using Identifiable data would also be a later Phase.

Phase 3 will aim to extend coverage to 100% of the health boards within a Scotland SDE target operating model.

The initial Phase 1 scope of the federation work is to develop process design and do proof-of-concept work. 10 expressions of interest have been received but four have been excluded as out-of-scope due to being commercial and/or ML/AI driven:

Kathy highlighted a number of **Learnings** so far:

- Engagement is key:
 - Collaboration cafés good format
 - Co-design around priority areas
 - PPIE in parallel
- SATRE was useful framework to discussion differences in ways of working
- Agreeing standards is difficult, but establishing equivalence is simpler
- Operating model differences created challenges in talking to the right people
- Continuous evolution of a model will be needed in years 2+
- Need to be able to access legal opinions

Discussion:

Kathy's session prompted considerable questions and discussion in an open session of around 30 minutes – see [YouTube](#) here ⁴ to follow this in full. A selected summary is below:

- Comments and questions around SATRE within federated governance for example:
 - Recognise that SATRE is a good building block for thinking about shared risk but also needs ongoing development
 - Having a spec to talk to worked well. Heat maps were engaging!
 - Request more on the detail of which SATRE aspects varied and where it worked well
 - Unknown expectations around compliance monitoring and the role of SATRE - don't want to be creating another accreditation steps for ourselves.
 - Disagreement around what the language means in the framework – each TRE in Scotland had to make its own assumptions about - similar experiences were mentioned in the room.
- Federated governance is one aspect of "federation" alongside the technical and the funding parts.
 - Often technical aspects of data sharing are not the problem, agreement is the problem! As challenges are not often technical, but political, and related to risk.
 - By delegating governance, we are delegating control which increases risk
 - Appropriate ways of making a decision can vary between data controllers, and may relate to data types.
 - This requires the trusted relationships. how can they be built and damaged? There is a lot of trust between the safe havens and the health boards. This seems to be creating an oversight methodology agreed between partners.
 - Specific approval processes, questions on e.g. what panels are convened or application forms used to support the Scottish system.

- Kathy discussed trust relationships - in answer to questions about how the delegated decision making could work between different risk appetites of the boards:
 - Collecting the applications helps demonstrate to all - Are we asking the same questions or trying to get the same understanding, even if we are doing it in different ways? Equivalence example.
 - All of the Health Boards want oversight and a route for retrospective learning - providing proofs of concept e.g. feedback loops
 - When decisions are made, they can be discussed across all controllers where they don't have the same risk appetite. Activities built on a history of decisions (precedent) is important – but makes making the first decision slower.
 - Continue to communicate that **scaling** is the intention, with a route to deliver that – consider what is low risk for now? What are simple/obvious things which we could start with (may be 500+ projects which would be easier to implement now)
 - **Scaling** also involves looking at opportunities for shared infrastructure, which is also financially appropriate cf. building in silos!
 - Reflects some of the historical work (e.g. all ISO 27001, so don't look too different in the technical standards)
 - Doing it in small steps makes it possible to move forwards. There is a **challenge to maintain the pace** when we do it at a national level, plus a **funding challenge**
 - It's taken Scotland 15y to get here. Decided 1yr ago that we needed to get on with this federation of governance
- Other examples of shared decision making across data controllers?
 - Crick - setting up a project involving multiple nations - difficulty of sovereignty - legal agreement embodies the expectations of the platforms and facilities. Who makes the data access decisions?
- Could Information Governance act as a service framework?
 - Scotland (and the UK TRE community) has not considered this yet

The group concluded we need to pin down the language so we can have effective conversations between actors. This will help scaling Information Governance.

- testing for "equivalence" as a term/practice is useful in its pragmatism
- The IG debate must not be separated from the technical
- Harmonisation of data at local levels is very hard. At a national level there is a greater pre-existing requirement for harmonisation, harmonisation of understanding of risk could be a way forward.

Close of Event:

The event concluded with a second word cloud question revisiting the question of what Information Governance means to people. The results are showing in the image below.

Compared to Figure 1, through the three hours discussion, there seemed to be a change in the words attendees were using to outline what IG means to them – indicating some shift towards seeing the complexity and nuances that have been discussed. *Proportionality*, and *collaboration* now balance *compliance*, *risk* and *security*. Hardly scientific but suggesting the session was helpful to those respondents.

Close: What 3 words do you *now* associate with information governance?
Wordcloud Poll 34 responses 15 participants

Figure 5: Word cloud summary of concluding question on Information Governance

The final poll asked participants their views on the structure of the discussion elements, as the meeting was all in plenary without breakout rooms. The immediate poll results are shown below: ~72% of the respondents felt this worked well or very well for them (grading 4 and 5); ~5% felt it did not work for them.

- An offline poll was also shared to allow for a more extensive capturing of feedback on the event. <https://forms.gle/ueVTWz2miojf73Hq9>

★ How did the plenary/breakout discussions format work for you?
Rating Poll 18 votes 18 participants

Everyone was thanked for the presentations and active involvement, and the event concluded on time.